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Research

Article

**ANALYSIS OF COMPLETE BLOOD PROFILE (CBC) IN
HEPATITIS PATIENTS**Dr. Tasmia Tahir¹, Dr. Khadija Tahir¹, Dr. Zeeshan Ahmad¹¹Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur

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Abstract:

Introduction and objectives: Liver is a pivotal organ of the body and play very important role in the metabolism. The main objective of the study is to find the complete blood analysis in hepatitis patients. **Methodology of the study:** This cross-sectional study was conducted at Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur during June 2019 to December 2019. 1.0 ml blood sample was taken from vein and blood was further processed for the estimation of CBC by using commercially available enzymatic kits of Random. **Results:** Our result indicated that platelet-related indices significantly differed between the HCV-infected group and the negative control group. Compared with the control group, the HCV-infected group had significantly lower platelet counts (PLT) and platelets counts (PCT) but significantly higher platelet distribution mean platelet volumes (MPV), and platelet-large cell ratios (P-LCR). **Conclusion:** Our results concluded that hepatitis directly effects on a human body and blood system, due to which RBC count and other values become low as compared to normal values.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Tasmia Tahir,

Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Liver is a pivotal organ of the body and play very important role in the metabolism. If there is any problem in the liver then the herbs or different plants play an important role for the treatment of liver disorders¹. There are a number of plants which shows hepatoprotective property. Hepatitis B and C viruses can lead to hepatocellular carcinoma and cirrhosis-related end-stage liver disease, which are potentially life-threatening liver diseases. Hepatitis B and C need immediate worldwide attention as the infection rates are too high. More than 240 million people globally have chronic (long-term) liver infections. Every year, about 600,000 people die because of the acute or chronic consequences of hepatitis B, and more than 350,000 people die from hepatitis C-related liver diseases worldwide².

In the Middle East and the Indian subcontinent, an estimated 2%–5% of the general population is chronically infected with hepatitis B. Countries with the highest reported prevalence rates of hepatitis C are located in Africa and Asia; areas with lower prevalence rates of hepatitis C include industrialized nations in North America and Northern and Western Europe³. Studies have been conducted in Pakistan to assess the prevalence as well as identify the various risk factors associated with hepatitis B and C. A meta-analysis indicates that the prevalence of hepatitis B and C in the general population in Pakistan is 2.4% (range, 1.4%–11.0%) and 3.0% (range, 0.3%–31.9%), respectively⁴.

In most of these studies, however, very few risk factors were included in one study at a time. Many risk factors have been identified worldwide, e.g., blood transfusion, IV drug abuse, profession (health care workers, barbers, etc), household

contact, sexual contact, surgical procedures, dental procedures, immune-compromised hemodialysis, skin tattoos, etc, but the ones responsible for the high prevalence of hepatitis B and C in our cities need to be identified⁵.

Objectives of the study

The main objective of the study is to find the complete blood analysis in hepatitis patients

METHODOLOGY OF THE STUDY:

This cross-sectional study was conducted at Bahawal Victoria Hospital, Bahawalpur during June 2019 to December 2019. The data was collected from 200 patients and compare these values with normal group. 1.0 ml blood sample was taken from vein and blood was further processed for the estimation of CBC (RBC's, WBC's, TP, Platelets count) by using commercially available enzymatic kits of Randox.

Statistical analysis

The data were sampled and entered into the SPSS version 19.0 worksheet for analysis.

RESULTS:

The data was collected from 200 patients. The mean age was 39.3 ± 10.8 years. There were 57.6% male and 42.4% female patients. Our result indicated that platelet-related indices significantly differed between the HCV-infected group and the negative control group. Compared with the control group, the HCV-infected group had significantly lower platelet counts (PLT) and plateletcrit counts (PCT) but significantly higher platelet distribution widths (PDW), mean platelet volumes (MPV), and platelet-large cell ratios (P-LCR). Restated, the HCV-infected group had lower PLT and PCT but higher MPV, PDW, and P-LCR. This implied that the HCV-infected group had larger, more irregular, and more numerous platelets compared to the controls.

Table 01: CBC of hepatitis patients of local population of Pakistan

Variable	HCV-infected group	t-test P	ANCOVA P #
Male	83 (57.6)		
Female	61 (42.4)	<0.001	
Age mean (sd)	39.3 ± 10.8	0.071	
WBC ($\times 10^3 \mu\text{l}$)	6.8 ± 1.9	<0.001	0.006
RBC ($\times 10^6 \mu\text{l}$)	4.9 ± 0.7	<0.001	0.024
HB (g/dl)	14.7 ± 1.5	<0.001	<0.001
HCT (%)	43.0 ± 3.9	<0.001	0.001
MCV (fl)	89.1 ± 8.0	0.243	0.122
MCH (pg)	30.5 ± 3.1	0.008	0.030

MCHC (g/dl)	34.2 ± 1.0	<0.001	0.005
PLT (×10 ³ μl)	222.3 ± 58.8	<0.001	<0.001
NEU (%)	56.4 ± 9.0	0.052	<0.001
LYM (%)	34.0 ± 8.2	0.270	0.648
MONO (%)	6.6 ± 1.8	<0.001	<0.001
EOS (%)	2.5 ± 1.6	0.630	0.174
BAS (%)	0.5 ± 0.3	0.140	0.230
RDW-SD (fl)	41.8 ± 2.9	0.013	0.055
RDW-CV (%)	13.3 ± 1.5	0.040	0.034
P-LCR (%)	31.7 ± 6.2	<0.001	<0.001
PCT (%)	0.2 ± 0.1	<0.001	<0.001
NEUT (×10 ³ μl)	3.9 ± 1.4	0.034	0.090
LYMPH (×10 ³ μl)	2.3 ± 0.7	<0.001	0.004
MONO (×10 ³ μl)	0.4 ± 0.1	<0.001	<0.001
EOS (×10 ³ μl)	0.2 ± 0.1	0.083	0.561
BAS (×10 ³ μl)	0.03 ± 0.02	0.463	0.789
TPO (pg/ml)	74.4 ± 66.3	<0.001	<0.001
ALT (IU/L)	35.5 ± 45.0	0.006	0.339

DISCUSSION:

Damage to the structural integrity of liver is reflected by an increase in the level of serum transaminase because these are cytoplasmic in location and are released into circulation after cellular damage⁶. It is generally accepted that the toxicity of carbon tetrachloride depends on the cleavage of the carbon-chlorine bond to generate a trichloromethyl free radical, and this free radical reacts rapidly with oxygen to form a trichloro methyl peroxy radical, which may contribute to the hepatotoxicity and subsequent increase in hepatic enzymes⁷.

Since previous studies indicate that thrombocytopenia results from chronic liver disease, we speculated that a haematological comparison between a healthy blood donor and a donor with HCV might reveal the impact of HCV on PLT and TPO; an improved understanding of this impact could help determine whether a donor has HCV⁸. This hypothesis was tested by investigating the relationships among haematological indices and TPO and HCV viral loads. The haematological indices and TPO were also evaluated in terms of predictive performance. Because of the varying consent given by the participants, the negative control group and HCV-infected group were not matched by age or gender. Therefore, ANCOVA

was used to adjust the statistical analysis for age and gender⁹.

We found that in our society, the important risk factors for hepatitis B and C are household contact, history of dental work, history of surgery, sexual contact, and history of transfusion (blood and its components)¹⁰.

CONCLUSION:

It is concluded that hepatitis directly effect on a human body and blood system, due to which RBC count and other values become low as compared to normal values. To enhance the early detection of HCV infection, further studies are needed to modify and improve existing screening procedures and to develop convenient supplemental screening flowcharts. Until then, the findings of this study should be applied cautiously.

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